

Untangling the future of diamond access: discussing quality standards for the re-communalization of scholarly publishing

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Abstract

This paper examines the future of Diamond Open Access as a non-commercial, community-driven model for scholarly publishing that challenges the growing marketization of research dissemination. Drawing on recent initiatives such as DIAMAS, Craft-OA, and the Diamond Future project, it analyzes tensions between academic autonomy and the heteronomy imposed by commercial publishers. The study reviews existing definitions and standards for diamond journals, highlighting efforts in Europe and Latin America to establish common criteria for quality, sustainability, and visibility. It emphasizes the need to move beyond universal rankings and impact factors toward context-sensitive, federated indexing systems—such as Latindex, SciELO, Redalyc, Biblat, and DOAJ—that reflect the diversity of academic communities. The paper argues for a re-communalization of scholarly publishing through institutional support, reliable indexation, and recognition of multi-indexed journals as legitimate indicators of quality. Ultimately, it proposes reclaiming academic control from corporate infrastructures by reinforcing autonomy, multilingualism, and bibliodiversity in global research evaluation and publication practices.

Introduction

The “future of academic publishing” is a recurring concern that returns repeatedly in the history of science, to the beat of the major shifts that occurred with digitalization and followed with the expansion of open access during the COVID-19 pandemic (Scheufen 2015; Ahmed, Al-Khatib, Boum II et al 2023). The proliferation of paid Open Access and hybrid journals is one of these relevant changes, one that generated a significant global asymmetry. Researchers affiliated in rich institutions that signed transformative agreements can access to “open access”, while others are forced to cover these charges with personal funds or strongly driven to publish in traditional subscription journals. Academic institutions are investing millions of euros in disseminating research that has already been publicly funded, and the detrimental effects of these trends are well-documented (Simard et al 2024; Frank, Foster & Pagliari 2022; Steinhart et al 2024). Scholarly communication becomes increasingly commodified, although highly diversified, comprising a wide array of publishing business models: from journals published by major commercial publishers, the one-size-fits-all mega-journals, up to those managed by University publishers or small, specialized publishing houses. In this context, the “gold” route

that was imagined by the open access movement in its beginnings became corrupted by diverse forms of paywalls (Chan et al 2020, Pinfield 2025).

In parallel, there are thousands of journals directly edited by university portals, independent research institutes or learned societies (Nazarovets & Taşkin 2025). This landscape is fed by non-commercial publishing platforms like Redalyc, AJOL or Scielo. Probably it is the extensive use of OJS what explains the resilience and continuous expansion of this kind of nonprofit community-led journals. A new term was created to name the open access journals that do not charge to read or publish: the “diamond” seemed the more valuable jewel to define it. *Diamondalisation* as a neologism was coined in due course (Mounier & Rooryck 2023) and it became an increasingly shared value, understood not only as a form of access to scholarly publishing, or merely as a journal business model.

Chan (2022) and others intervened with a cautionary note on this new denomination because it is used in the same neoliberal framework that turned "gold OA" into a revenue stream for publishers. Besides, the fact that this mineral embodies the very nature of colonial extraction is indeed a good reason to discuss its very definition or even abandon its use. However, beyond the labels, the main causal factor of this distinction resides in the marketization of open access and scholarly publishing as such. This commercial publishing is producing a drain of time, money, trust and loss of control by the academic community (Beigel, Brockington, Crosetto et al 2025). Academic autonomy is at stake in front of the aggressive intrusions of the publishing industry and points out the need to straighten the future of diamond open access towards a re-communalization of the journals.

This involves necessarily discussion around the quality standards of academic edition and how to endow the non-commercial journals with symbolic value, thereby incentivizing researchers to choose them for disseminating their findings, within a conservative evaluation system still reticent to change. This challenge is directly linked to the reforms promoted by organizations like COARA, DORA, and FOLEC, widely desired yet largely unachieved across institutions and countries. To untangle the future of diamond access requires bridging the gap between the Open Science movement and the evaluation reform (Waltman, 2025). One way to do so is by placing in front a truly contextualized, multiscale, scrutiny of the concept of excellence.

Many think that one of the drivers of the exclusion that features gold Open Access and the growth of commercial publishing was the Plan S and the various incentives and policy regulations in the European area. Indeed, this regional actor played a significant role in a rapid change that affected the dynamics of scholarly publishing not only in Europe but globally. However, it is fair to recognize that these negative effects have been considered by the Coalition S and currently they are fostering several global projects to boost diamond publishing. Initiatives such as the DIAMAS project, The Diamond Discovery Hub, The Global Diamond Summits, Craft-OA, and the newest Almasi project have made substantial contributions to fostering quality, sustainability and visibility of diamond journals. The underlying doubt is always regarding the

limits or the maneuver margin that the UE open access strategy has to confront the interests of the commercial publishers.

Despite the numerous reports and research projects that attempt to describe diamond publishing, there remains another significant gap concerning the global landscape of these journals. What kind of audiences they reach, the indexation services they have, the type of management used and the institutional publishers that support them. This is particularly true for Latin America, where thousands of academic journals are published but remain underrepresented in traditional databases and indexes. The DIAMAS report published in 2021 stated that there was evidence of around 29,000 active diamond journals. But the observation was limited to half of this universe: the existing lists of the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). The available studies at journal level point out these limitations, while there are several efforts to overcome this issue (Beigel et al 2023; Taubert, Sterzik & Bruns 2024; Beigel, 2025; Nazarovets, Taskin & Laakso 2025; Kulczycki et al, 2025).

Plainly in this direction, the recently launched *Diamond Future* project is a collaborative venture nurtured by research teams based in Argentina and Germany. On the Argentinian side it builds up with the OLIVA project, developed at the Research Center for the Circulation of Knowledge (CECIC; Universidad Nacional de Cuyo) and the HERA Platform¹ (Universidad Nacional de La Plata). On the German end, it interacts with the Berlin University Alliance-Objective 3 and the newly established Servicestelle Diamond Open Access (SeDOA). Its main aim is to create an interactive website for researchers and evaluators of different research assessment systems to find conceptual resources, diamond landscape mappings and curated journal lists that can be of help in the individual choice of a journal or the valuation of publishing venues in evaluation processes. *Diamond Future* intends to systematize a contextualized situation on the existent definitions of diamond access to build the conceptual framework and input needed to create a global registry of quality indexed diamond journals. The website aims to create a prototype of a platform capable of providing real time reports on diamond journals by discipline and country, including different indicators of interest for researchers and evaluators.

This paper is part of this effort and is nurtured by previous research projects, among them the global cartography of diamond indexed journals (Beigel, 2025) that has been updated to June 2025. In the first section, we delve into the tensions between autonomy and heteronomy in scholarly publishing attempting to describe the actors and infrastructures that participate in a trend of inclusive openness and those who expand the marketization and exclusion. Secondly, we discuss the challenges of Diamond journals in terms of sustainability, coverage, visibility and legitimacy. Afterwards, we focus on the review of the state of arts in terms of the definition of ¿diamond? non-profit, or community-led journals by focusing in the role of universities in this conjuncture. Then, we address the quality standards for diamond publishing that are under discussion in the various active initiatives in Europe and Latin America to reinforce the critical

¹ The Tool for Scholarly Resources Assessment (HERA), is an already existing web-based tool that aims to simplify, streamline, and support the process of determining the quality and impact of a scholarly resource.

issue of academic autonomy in this debate. Finally, we propose a way forward, pushing the de-marketization of scholarly publishing by bringing the concept of “indexation” back in the evaluation debate.

The tensions between autonomy and heteronomy in open access publishing

The current trends existing in open access publishing give enough evidence of how openness can be featured by exclusiveness: two sides of a phenomena that seem opposite in nature. It has been extensively discussed that the development of the gold route by commercial publishers led to a new paywall for authors by transferring the costs of publication through the “article processing charges” (APCs). The big scholarly publishers not only recur to price authors for increasing revenues, but the dominant strategy is also to convene millionaire read & publish agreements with universities and funding institutions. The lack of transparency of publishing costs and APC prices contributes to the growth of the community’s distrust over open access. Universities and funders are highly concerned about paying thrice for the full process of research and its dissemination: as salary support for researchers; to buy journal subscriptions; and to subsidize APCs (Pagliari, 2015).

There are different paths towards open access co-existing conflictingly at the global scale, and the tension between them is not only determined by the degrees of openness/closedness but related to the poles of autonomy/heteronomy. Figure 1 shows different combinations in this space of conflict that we organize in resemblance to the way Bourdieu describes the properties of a given field. To the right we see the features of openness and to the left, the characteristics of closedness. But combined with the vertical axis and read more practically starting from the center, where both axes cross each other, we can see four quadrants. The upper quadrants are featured by exclusion and heteronomy, pushed by the commercial actors or by the traditional asymmetries of the world academic system. In the lower quadrants, on the contrary, we see high levels of inclusion and academic autonomy but with different degrees of circulation, being the left inferior quadrant a space with limited openness due to sovereignty issues or the protection required by subaltern groups.

Figure 1

The space of disputes in scholarly publishing

In the left upper quadrant, the big commercial publishers dominate through the constellation made of the Scopus-Clarivate publishing platforms (See Figure 2). The increasing concentration of scholarly services and the fact that they still hold great part of the credibility of the academic community makes this sector also dominant in terms of global value for research assessment. Contrary to inclusiveness, these commercial publishers need to offer exclusive goods and services that can guarantee access to the global value of excellence, which is (by definition) scarce and exceptional. The upper right quadrant is compliant with the main conditions for openness, such as interoperability, FAIR principles. But it leads to severe exclusion in the frame of the gold business model where the big commercial publishers also transfer the costs of publishing to individual authors that are affiliated to institutions that cannot afford read & publish agreements.

Frankly opposed to the heteronomous and exclusive mainstream circuit in the upper right quadrant is the inclusive and autonomous environment represented in the right lower quadrant in Figure 1. The main drivers for this path in open Access have been the regional publishing platforms and portals such as Latindex, Scielo, Redalyc, Biblat, AJOL, that have established conditions for quality journals in multiple languages (See Figure 2). Given the fact that the established hierarchies in the academic world give scarce value to these journals, inclusive open science can be less visible at a global scale, but noticeable at a regional level. However, it embodies a critical effort to preserve interculturality and foster the human right to science.

Figure 2

Actors at play in the dynamics of openness

In the left lower quadrant, we see inclusive closedness, a pole that is featured by a restricted circulation of knowledge which, on the other hand, is mostly locally valued. Among these we may see scientific output that is disseminated in non-indexed journals, numerous initiatives for the management of scientific information and digital platforms that are created without permanent identifiers and many other similar experiences. During the discussions held in the UNESCO Advisory Committee for Open Science, the risks of openness were discussed towards the need to protect subaltern communities, indigenous knowledge, or scientific information subject to extraction under unequal power relations: *open all that is possible and close only what is necessary was the basis of the debate*. But this was critical not only to *protect*, but also to *respect* the rights of the indigenous groups to the autonomous government of their native knowledge. The CARE principles were born in the midst of this tension and today represent one of the main guidelines for a transition to inclusive openness: collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

The predominantly local value of these publishing circuits is related to a deeper problem, because structural inequalities in the production and circulation of knowledge have had repercussions on the very criteria for evaluating science at a global level, reinforcing the hierarchization of knowledge produced in central countries and its consequent subordination of knowledge generated in non-hegemonic countries. Kraemer-Mbula et al. (2019) argue that the universalization of the idea of “excellence” encouraged many funding agencies and governments in Southern countries to demand certain levels of performance in journals with a high impact factor as an indicator of quality. The growing influence that this had on funding decisions, and success in academic careers promoted a growing distancing from social needs and the local research agenda.

Closedness is not only featured by the need to protect subaltern groups from violence or the extraction of native knowledge. It can also be used by governments to defend digital sovereignty. From a democratic perspective, governments must protect citizens' personal data and national economic interests. Steinhart et al (2024) argue that digital sovereignty can be defined as the right of a nation, region, or other political entity to assert control over its digital infrastructure and data, on behalf of its citizens. However, in an authoritarian regime, this can be used as an excuse to limit academic freedom and exert social control over the citizens.

Latin America represents an alternative open access publishing circuit, with federated infrastructures and diamond journals that are community managed and driven by the principle of science as a common good. However, the “mainstream” circuit still concentrates the belief of the internationalized researchers in the performative effects of the high-impact journals, and this prevents them from changing their paths of circulation at risk of losing recognition. SciELO, Redalyc and Latindex have made enormous efforts to increase visibility and impact, and this regional circuit is sustained by governmental agencies and public institutions. But the academic evaluation defined by these same organizations depreciates these journals, resulting in a form of alienation still unresolved. It is a heterogeneous region with diverse scientific policies and governance approaches of the scientific information systems that co-exist in a noncommercial publishing ecosystem. The relevant experience in federated infrastructures by LA Referencia and its local technology can play critical role in a just transition towards de-marketization and inclusive open science.

The current challenges of Diamond journals: sustainability, coverage, visibility, legitimacy

The dominance of the Web of Science (Clarivate) or Scopus in the value regime in academia has been discussed by extensive literature, which points out that these indexing services exclude vast circuits of scholarly communication that have existed for decades. The resilience of these publishing venues seems related both to the institutional support they have received and to the survival of national and regional multilingual academic audiences. Kulczycki et al. (2025) examined scholarly publishing beyond the oligopolies of commercial publishers, showing a more diverse and nuanced picture. Using national databases and the ISSN center, they compared the national journals from 7 countries, 3 from Europe and 4 from Latin America. The latter emerges distinctly by institutional publishing driven by public universities, often relying on public funding and the engagement of scholars in the editorial venture. Conversely, the European countries are featured by journals edited by professional associations and learned societies, which offer organizational stability and institutional legitimacy, yet not all have been able to prioritize academic autonomy over commercial interests.

Despite the differences in terms of the institutional publishers, a commonality is evident: in both regions, when the “national” scholarly publishing is observed by multisource databases, the

landscape emerges deeply embedded in non-commercial environments. Dagiane and Aibar (2025) argue that control over a community-managed domestic publishing infrastructure is a key factor shaping the autonomy of a national academic system. Such venues provide robust alternatives to the oligopolistic models prevalent in the Anglophone ecosystem, fostering multilingualism and more diverse research agendas (Kulczycki et al 2025). Most of these journals, as expected, are Diamond. Frequently, these journals are international in terms of scope and the quality of expert peer review. However, those that are not included in the journal rankings suffer scarce visibility and de-legitimation.

The most prestigious journals that reach high-impact performance and legitimation are irremediably affected by the increasing number of manuscripts in all disciplines, along with the difficulties to solve peer review processes and other editorial tasks. This has inclined many learned societies to transfer editorship to commercial publishers, this being a common case in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). Differently, in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) most journals are edited at universities, which found institutional support to prevail over time (Late, Guns et al., 2024). One of the main consequences of the commercial management of the journals is the systematical market intrusions in the journal's publishing flux that ends up taking control of the entire editorial process causing a clash of scientific and economic rationalities (Taubert 2012).

The extent to which these interferences meddle with the assessments traditionally performed by editors and peers puts in question scholarly editorship itself and the quality of these judgments. Eventually, it also may broaden the gray zone of predatory publishing (Siversten, 2021). The scourge of increasing APC prices and its exclusion effect has highlighted the relevance of diamond journals as an alternative path to publish in community-led scholarly venues. However, some studies have characterized diamond journals as suffering from artisan editorship (OPERAS, 2021). Nazarovets (2025) argues that the visibility of the university journals remains limited and is partially attributable to a lack of international submissions, as researchers often prefer journals with greater global reach and recognition. The barriers to international visibility include language restrictions, limited indexing in global databases and a lack of standardization in metadata practices. And these barriers create a cyclical issue where journals struggle to attract high-quality international submissions, thereby reinforcing their local orientation. On their part, many stakeholders may believe that to foster diamond journals means to go back in times when journals were handcrafted by an altruist group of scholars.

The Latin American publishing circuit has survived beyond commodification and has resisted the devaluation derived from by impact assessment. There are thousands of Diamond open access journals in all disciplines, published by universities, whose quality is determined by the evaluation in indexing systems such as Latindex, SciELO, Redalyc and Biblat. This regional experience is significant nowadays as result of both universities and funders providing support. So, it becomes critical to insist in the relationship between visibility and legitimacy. Still today, journals on the Web of Science (Clarivate) and Scopus rankings are better recognized in

research assessment and highly rewarded in career promotion. This distinguishing line of valuation was established through several means, including salary incentives, hierarchical classifications and other symbolic rewards that had direct incidence in the research agendas (Hicks, Wouters et al., 2015; Marginson, 2021; Ràfols, Ciarli, & Chavarro, 2015).

Compared to the commercial circuit, an important feature of these Diamond journals is the resilience of autonomous editorship (Beigel, 2025). But to go beyond resilience means to build academic reputation for these journals to become a desirable choice for researchers around the world. The concern for visibility is long-standing in Latin America. Its four regional indexation systems (SciELO, Latindex, Redalcy and Biblat) constitute restrictive collections based on numerous criteria regularly revised (Merlo Vega & Montoya-Roncancio, 2023). Latindex was particularly active in framing the discussion on the difference between “excellence” and “quality” (Cetto & Alonso-Gamboa, 2011). After more than two decades of devoted efforts in the region, the key issue seems to be to achieve legitimacy in the evaluation processes where recognition is at stake. The paradox becomes apparent when confronted to the existing national classification systems in the region (such as Publindex, Qualis) where these quality journals are devalued constantly by the value conferred to the impact indicators.

The definition of ¿diamond? ¿non-profit? journals

The use of the concept of “diamond” for no fee open access journals is under scrutiny for many reasons -among these the use of a symbolic stone of colonialism as mentioned in the introduction. In front of the increasing marketization of scholarly publishing, several projects are discussing definitions for these kinds of journals with unrestricted, no-fee access to authors and readers. Beyond labels, although more appropriate denominations may emerge, the debate on diamond journals exceeds paywalls. It stresses the features of these journals as community-led and owned by academic organizations with a research mission. To our understanding, the debate shall dig into the core of the problem of scholarly publishing, which is the fact that it became a profitable market, increasingly independent from the scientific field.

In Figure 3 we selected 4 relevant sources that propose definitions of diamond journals. The German Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAG) is interesting because it aims to the curation of an open dataset of diamond journals published in the country. It also involves articulated efforts on the national scale towards the dynamization of Diamond Open Access through innovative concepts while increasing efficiency, providing better coordination, organization and information.

Figure 3

4 DEFINITIONS OF DIAMOND JOURNALS

coalition S-DOAS (for IPSP): Diamond Open Access refers to a **scholarly publication**

model in which journals and platforms **do not charge fees** to either authors or readers. Diamond Open Access journals are **community-driven, academic-led, and academic-owned** publishing initiatives. <https://www.coalitions.org/diamond-open-access/>

Global Diamond Summit Toluca 2023: Diamond Open Access (OA) is a **scholarly communication**

model in which research outputs are openly available, **without charging fees** to either authors or readers. In this model, all content-related elements are **led and owned by scholarly communities**. <https://globaldiamantoa.orgU/Global-Summit-Conclusions-Way-Forward.pdf>

DOAG-Germany: A diamond OA journal offers immediate open access to all content

published by the journal, **without charging any fees** from authors. Neither journals that charge article processing charges (APC) nor hybrid OA or delayed OA journals meet this definition <https://pub.uni-bielefeld.de/record/2965484>

CRAFT-OA: 6 criteria (in collaboration with the community)

Persistent identification-ISSN Scholarly journal: described evaluation process
Open licences
No fees of any kind
Open to all authors
Community-owned by public or not-for-profit organisations with a research mission and scholarship (ownership status on its webpage).

The DIAMAS project gathers 23 organizations from 12 European countries, well versed in OA academic publishing and scholarly communication. It has mapped institutional publishers and service providers, focusing on venues that do not charge fees to authors or readers. To support the diamond model, it has also created the DOAS standards, which we will discuss further. [CRAFT-OA](#), on its part, proposes 6 criteria for diamond publishing as defined by the task force in collaboration with the community among which the determination of a “scholarly” journal depends on the selection of papers via an explicitly described evaluation process before and/or after publication. No fees of any kind can be charged, and the journal should state this as such on its webpage. It considers voluntary contributions and donations acceptable, as long as this is not a condition for publication. A well-known problem to comply with this standard is the lack of transparency in payment information. Simard, Butler, Alperin & Haustein (2024) noticed that temporarily waiving APCs was a commonly used strategy by the Big 5 for-profit publishers, all of which adds more instability to the data on costs collected for a given journal.

Among the initiatives to foster diamond publishing, we highlight the recently created [Diamond Discovery Hub \(DDH\)](#), that intends to be a comprehensive registry of institutionally published and scholar-led Open Access Journals in Europe. The DDH will operationalize the “Diamond Open Access” concept through comprehensive parameters and functionalities for data collection. It aims to make new facets of diamond publishing visible, such as governance and mission and to create a curated list of European journals that comply with the 6 criteria (See Figure 3): Scholarly journal; Open Access with open licenses; No fees; Open to all authors; Community-Owned and persistent identifiers.

Another relevant initiative is the [ALMASI](#) project aiming to align and mutualize nonprofit open access publishing services internationally. The main diagnosis of the initiative is that non-profit publishing solutions exist but are scattered, lacking a unified structure. In this context, ALMASI

aims to build a Diamond Open Access ecosystem across Europe, Africa and Latin America, offering free publishing services for authors and readers. ALMASI will map existing non-profit services, set quality standards, and provide training for editors and staff. ALMASI strives to make knowledge globally accessible, benefiting diverse scholarly communities.

The global debate on the definition of Diamond Open Access took a big step forward during the Diamond Open Access Global Summits held in 2023 and 2024. The Toluca declaration in the Mexican summit emphasized the global engagement as the way forward, with the organizing partners reinforcing their commitment to this approach. The Cape Town summit recommended the establishment of a Global Federation for Diamond Open Access, hosted by UNESCO. This distributed and federated infrastructure was envisioned as a network of national Diamond Capacity Centers and Regional Capacity Hubs similar to SciELO, Redalyc and Latindex. Beyond the realistic progress of this federation, the shared goal of these summits is centering social justice and building an inclusive and equitable diamond open access movement.

Mounier & Rooryck (2025) argue that diamond publishing is more than just the absence of fees for authors and readers, because the problem lies in the historical shift in academic publishing from being managed by academic communities to being controlled by large commercial publishers. Accordingly, the structural problem is not only to ensure complete free open access, but to preserve the academic autonomy of the journals and regain complete control by the research community. They underscore the necessity of reclaiming autonomy through community-run publication models, although they argue that this should not be equated with 'institutional publishing'. "Institutions nurture, protect, and confer status upon academics, yet they also create a scientific field marked by power struggles, unequal resource distribution, and social dynamics that may have little to do with knowledge creation. (...) In other words, collaborating with private, even commercial, publishers outside of their institutions is seen by some academics as a form of liberation from the power structures within the academic system" (Mounier & Rooryck 2025).

Recommunalization of scholarly publishing: the role of universities

Let's focus now on the consensual feature of "community-owned" that diamond publishing seems to have or aspire. What does this mean in terms of the concrete anchorage of the journals? According to DOAS these include but are not limited to research performing organizations (RPO) and organizations connected to RPOs (university libraries, university presses, faculties, and departments), research institutes, and scholarly societies. What is an institutional publisher and what role is expected from the service providers? How can we assure that the latter will not lead new forms of marketization? All the definitions in Figure 3 state that the journal title must be owned by public or not-for-profit organizations (or parts thereof) whose mission includes performing or promoting research and scholarship.

The [European University Association](#) (EUA) has recently addressed the situation of scholarly publishing arguing that it diverged from its original purposes and drifted away from the needs of the communities ignoring bibliodiversity and multilingualism, imposing high costs on researchers and research performing organisations and threatening core academic values such as trust and integrity (EUA, 2025). EUA points out that a robust, sustainable and interoperable scholarly publishing ecosystem requires each university to properly curate their research contributions and outputs, through institutional or shared infrastructure and services (e.g. repositories, publishing platforms, and CRIS systems). It argues that the universities should support and promote the use of rights retention to regain academic ownership of scholarly communication, raising awareness of the systemic issues in scholarly publishing and engaging researchers to build support for long term cultural change” (EUA, 2025). The [International Science Council](#), on its part, discussed the principles for scientific publishing recommending the respect of diverse traditions and biodiversity in different disciplines and regions. In line with the EUA it argues that the governance of dissemination of scientific knowledge should be in the hands of the scientific community (ISC, 2025).

Rooryck (2025) rightly argues that the role of scholarly communities has not been addressed yet and it is crucial for a deeper understanding of Diamond dynamics. “Less formal than institutions and incorporated organizations, they resemble fluid entities, constantly forming and dissolving, lacking clear boundaries and governance structures. (...In contrast) A journal represents a community that is perfectly capable of self-organisation. Glossa: a journal of general linguistics is a Diamond OA journal in linguistics that sprang from the ashes of Elsevier owned *Lingua* in 2016, when its Editorial Team and Board, as well as its reader and author community, decided to abandon *Lingua* over a disagreement about journal ownership, Open Access, and the affordability of APCs. Eight years later, the move of the community to the new journal has been an unmitigated success: the journal recently published its 1000th article.” (Rooryck, 2025). The definition of the journals as research communities is related to an active specialized audience featured by a double practice of authorship and readership.

Nevertheless, the Glossa-Lingua example can also be considered more an exception than the rule. Our perspective based on a field approach also stresses the symbolic power struggles and the conflicts around segmenting classifications such as the concept of “excellence”. It entails tensions and asymmetries among institutions and between geographical spaces, which are differently equipped in terms of resources. However, scholarly publishing currently faces such a degree of marketization that has evolved into a detachment of the “mainstream” circuit from the scientific field. In practice, this occurred through an extraction of the scientific authority of academic editorship, placing the publishing decisions in hands of the commercial technical staff and computational managing (Beigel, 2025a). The scholarly publishing industry detached in this way from both kinds of scientific capital at stake in the academic field according with Bourdieu (2022): the capital of what can strictly be called scientific authority, which tends to be more international, and the temporal power over the scientific world which tends to be more national.

The latter, traditionally built through institutions, rectors and deans, scientific administrators, public research policies or funds, have participated of this sort of brain drain to the commercial publishers. But they can be instrumental in regaining academic control of scholarly publishing. In effect, national fields, academic institutions and disciplines are empirically observable, while it is more difficult to link journals with research communities nowadays. In this sense, the proposal by Gatti (2025) to extend the concept of community to infrastructures is interesting because many organizations supporting Diamond Open Access such as PKP, OpenEdition or Redalyc were established by scholars who developed these systems to meet the needs of their own journals. “Over time, however, the tools they created have evolved into shared infrastructures, supporting dozens, and eventually hundreds, of journals with comparable features. These infrastructures embody a vision aligned closely with that of a scholarly community, thus laying the groundwork for community building around them. As these infrastructures scale, however, they progressively enter a new dimension, moving further from the initial community-focused logic centered on a single or limited set of journals” (Gatti, 2025).

This kind of increasing infrastructural growth brings constraints associated with human resource management and large-scale financial sustainability for thousands of journals. Accordingly, it is wiser to produce synergy between the existing non-commercial publishing platforms (such as SciELO, Redalyc, OJS-PKP, Open Edition, Érudit) and the universities as publishing institutions that host community-led journals. In sum, this debate is critical to advance in the definition of a community-led journal. To pledge for re-communalization is not a structural solution itself, when it is understood as a naive return to the good old days of the small journals meant for the “best and the brightest”. Indeed, journals are part of a field that struggles over the possession of a scarce symbolic capital featured by scientific prestige, but the more multiscale publishing circuits are open to all, the more diversified research agendas and recognition paths can evolve.

Pampel et al. (2024) argue that bridging the gap for community-driven publication means strategic infrastructure support by comprehensive, large-scale funding organizations. Sustainable publication structures can be found in university libraries with their established services, expertise, and strong networks. These are well-positioned to serve as active publication service providers for scholarly communities. Community-driven journals are responsible for maintaining the content quality of publications, ensured using recognized peer review procedures that align with good scientific practice. University libraries, or Journal Portals managed by the Institutional Repository, as is the case in some universities, appear as one relevant organization to provide publishing services to several journals under compliance with these shared principles. They can establish direct collaboration with disciplinary communities within the university or related organizational structures, such as learned societies. Collaboration should be participatory while allowing the journals to remain autonomous, operating openly and interoperable with platforms that give access to broad audiences. Libraries are there to provide indexation to the material published in the institutional journals, data, and software in a machine-readable format, ensuring transparency and long-term

accessibility to the published material. Successful stories of university journals are based on the use of open-source software and non-profit managing systems such as OJS-PKP.

Beyond the theoretical discussion around autonomy and institutionalization, the empirical path observed in diamond publishing in the region where the phenomenon is most resilient is its development within a particular “infrastructure”: the university portals. In another work we mapped 786 university portals that publish more than 11.000 diamond journals in Latin America. These institutional structures have played a central role fulfilling the digitalization and professionalization of academic publishing in the region (Beigel, 2025c). Located in the libraries or the institutional repository with a centralized publishing policy, these portals could mediate between the institutional power struggles and the disciplinary conflicts between faculties. Accordingly, it seems more feasible to support quality diamond publishing in this kind of institutional framework that secures ownership and sustainability. Academic freedom should be guaranteed and the autonomy of the research community that is behind each journal.

Diamondization, widely desired increasingly in the globe, will find different paths according to the situation of each region and the circuits that cross through them. In the case of Latin America, the current commercial threats on scholarly publishing and the gigantism in terms of written papers do not foresee solutions based on supporting isolated good journals led by un-institutionalized communities with the help of service providers. In contrast, it seems more feasible to reinforce diamond journals supporting centralized editorial teams within the University libraries protecting them from heteronomous leaks or defection to the commercial publishers.

The quality standards for diamond community-led scholarly publishing

Considering altogether the Global Summits on Diamond Open Access (Toluca and Cape Town) and the related initiatives discussed before, we can affirm marketization and the consequent asymmetries emerging from paid open access, cannot be solved solely with actions to support diamond journals. The most difficult challenge is to change the researchers’ choice of a journal, because this is not just an individual decision but a multicausal result of the evaluative cultures and the reputation regimes at stake, the incentives and available funds, the individual attitudes towards open access, the career-stage, the institutional contexts among other factors. The creation of new sources informing community-led journals is critical to contribute to the necessary interaction between the open science reform and the research assessment reform. In this venture, interculturality, multilingualism and bibliodiversity must prevail along with the acknowledgement of the variety of journal structures and editorial models for diamond scholarly publishing.

Considering the relevance of the publishers in the definition of diamond journals, the knowledge about this aspect is still limited and there are several classifications in the available literature.

We have discussed the need to deepen the observation of the difference between what Ulrich's database calls "Corporate author" and "Commercial Publisher" because it is instrumental to define ownership and academic autonomy (Beigel, 2025a). Taşkın, Pölönen, Kulczycki & Laakso (2025) propose to classify three broad publisher types by primary function: 1) professional publishers, focused on publishing scholarly journals and books; 2) research organizations, dedicated to research and higher education; and 3) scholarly societies, organized researcher communities aiming to advance their fields. According to this study, while universities and societies may operate professional publishing activities such as university presses, publishing is not their primary function. From this organizational perspective they propose to include in the category of "professional publishers" all types of commercial publishers observed in the journals indexed in the Web of Science.

Although general publishing is not one of the main functions of universities or research institutions, academic editorship has been born, shaped and fed by learned societies and universities. The scientific journals were not created by the publishing market, on the contrary, they have been progressively acquired by the commercial firms because of their increasing profit. Outside the mainstream publishing circuit, academic editorship continued in hand of the universities as has been highlighted by the recent studies on thousands of active university journals (Nazarovets & Taşkın 2025; Beigel 2025c). In a study observing national publishing, the landscape looks very different from the WoS journals: the category of commercial publishers represent a minimal share of the journals edited in Finland (1.6%), Colombia (0.2%), and Mexico (2.5%), Argentina (4.07%) and Brazil (6.5%), while with a relatively more notable share in Turkey (12.1%) and Poland (8.2%). The rest of the journals are mostly published and owned by learned societies and universities (Kulczycki, Alonso Gamboa, Beigel et al 2025).

Let's now analyze the commercial/noncommercial stake in the recent approaches regarding the standards for diamond journals. The DIAMAS project established a set of 7 standards for Diamond journals considering: 1) funding, 2) ownership, 3) open science, 4) editorial quality, 5) technical efficiency, 6) visibility and 7) equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB). The other initiatives discuss similar standards but add new insights and it is an opportune time to systematize all these inputs to reach a consensus. The Diamond Open Access Summit held in Toluca (México) for example, proposed seven facets of diamond Open access: 1) equity, 2) knowledge as a public good, 3) community-driven, 4) diversity, 5) transitioning to diamond, 6) research assessment and recognition, and 7) multi-level cooperation. These facets can be considered features of existing journals, but also an ideal to be reached. Accordingly, we prepared a database with all the published reports, proceedings and projects to analyze the concepts used to define the diamond journals' quality standards. As can be seen in Figure 4, the most prominent words that cross-through all the initiatives, in order of frequency are: Quality, Institution, Open Access, Output, COARA, Metrics. Grouped around the DOAS 7 standards we can see that a set of concepts exceed some of these standards arguing around issues that can frame additional standards.

research quality can be considered, because of its importance, as an independent standard from editorial quality.

Figure 5

Concepts linked to “editorial quality”

The other DIAMAS standard that appears within a complex network of concepts surrounds the institution and standard 2 related to legal ownership, scholarly mission and governance. The role played by institutions in guaranteeing academic autonomy appears clearly in a different node, separating legal ownership from an active institutional publisher that appears linked to professors, academic freedom and institutional publishing policies (See Figure 6). We argue that a clear distinguishment in this standard is critical in order to prevent journals that are still formally owned by academic institutions but have transferred governance of the journals to a commercial publisher.

Figure 6

Concepts related to “legal ownership, scholarly mission and governance”

In sum, it may be interesting to add 2 standards to the DIAMAS list in order to represent the diverse concepts at work in this textual analysis and strengthen the path towards the re-communalization of scholarly publishing. The 9 standards, as they emerge from the expansion of the DOAS list would be: 1) funding; 2) legal ownership and scholarly mission; 3) academic editorship; 4) editorial quality; 5) peer review and research integrity; 6) open science 7) technical service efficiency; 8) visibility and 9) EDIB, gender and multilingualism.

A way forward: bringing indexation back in

The debate over the quality of the journals should acknowledge the pervasive effects of the standardization produced by an *excellence* value regime based on the accumulation of the impact factor. This quantitative indicator and the multiple rankings in use showed performative in establishing which journals are the most aspiring for the “best and the brightest” researchers. To produce a significant change in the situation, accordingly, it is critical to take distance from any universal standardization and homogenizing ranking. Diverse and multiscale publishing circuits should be valued according to their social and academic relevance. The measurement of the real circulation of a given paper, in terms of citations, may find an inclusive indicator in the future, but in the meantime, re-communalization seems to us as the urgent task.

To foster publishing in quality autonomous journals there are different means. Sivertsen, Pölönen & Røeggen (2025) mention a wide range of community-based journal evaluations: from national journal lists, quality indexing systems and disciplinary curated registries can be considered. An international survey on publishing practices and APC costs examined the factors considered by the researchers to select a journal to publish and the features assigned to a prestigious venue. Rankings and the impact factor played a relevant role in the options but

across disciplines the factor with major incidence to determine prestige was indexation (Beigel, Bruccoleri, Isuani, Pacanaro Trinca & van Schalkwyk 2025). This means that beyond the journal rankings, the fact that a journal is part of a certain collection is valued. And this brings us back to the ambiguous idea of indexation, one of the strings that could be untangled to foster a diamond future.

During some time now, the main criticism to the use of the impact factor is posed on the fact that this indicator replaces the expert review of the individual contributions of the researchers by manipulable indicators that only inform about the journals. The impact factor indeed fostered the apparition of journal rankings that stratified in quartiles an index that was originally understood as a list in which inclusion was a proof of quality. But not all indexation systems evolved in the same direction. By the time the Science Citation Index was created in 1964, other citation indexes were created in Latin America with the goal of creating a catalogue of quality journals where the regional output was published. These were intended to inform researchers and institutions and to facilitate access and circulation of this knowledge (Cetto, Alonso Gamboa & Córdoba, 2010; Reyna Espinosa, 2015). The first experiences were the *Biblioteca Regional de Medicina* (BIREME, 1967), *Citas Latinoamericanas en Ciencias Sociales y Humanas* (CLASE, 1975) which is celebrating 50 years, and the *Indice de revistas latinoamericanas en Ciencias* (PERIODICA, 1978).

The use of the term “citation index” was understood as the compilation of references of Latin American journals that appeared in the lists in the publications received in the libraries (Antonio Sánchez, Interview, 2025). This is how these indexation systems were outlined, and their development in the current *Bibliografía Latinoamericana* (BIBLAT, UNAM-México) and Latindex continued offering a catalogue of quality journals (Sánchez, Carrillo & Durán, 2021). Scielo and Redlayc, on their part provide a similar service evaluating journal entrance and exit from their catalogues based on a rigorous set of criteria. In addition, these latter provide their services as publishing platforms with access to metadata at the article level and advanced searching engines.

The problem with the term “indexation” is that currently it is used to name the process of harvesting references by different types of platforms, citation indexes and multiuse data bases. OpenAlex, Scopus, Crossref, Dimensions, Lens, WoS, Google Scholar are commonly referred to as “indexing systems”, but there are several differences in between them. Zheng, Miao, Bu, & Larivière (2025) argue that citations indexes play a crucial role for understanding how science is produced, disseminated, and used. WoS and Scopus operate on proprietary platforms that require costly subscriptions, limiting access for financially constrained researchers and institutions. Visser, van Eck & Waltman (2021) compared the most important bibliographical sources and argue that their value depends on many different elements: coverage, completeness and accuracy of the data provided. The proprietary nature of these datasets also restricts data sharing, as researchers are bound by licenses that prohibit free data exchange and transparency in collaborative projects. In response to these limitations, OpenAlex was

developed by the nonprofit organization OurResearch to provide an inclusive, publicly accessible bibliographic dataset for the global research community, providing a freely available database with a particular emphasis in the coverage of non-English speaking countries (Zheng, Miao, Bu, & Larivière 2025).

Nevertheless, there is a relevant technical difference between OpenAlex and the citation indexes that is generally overlooked: WoS, Scopus, Latindex, Rdealyc or SciELO are expert-curated journal lists. They index only documents that are published in the journals that are subject to an evaluation for admission in each core collection. Crossref on its part, indexes the references of those works published in the journals included in a set of publishers depending on the use of persistent identifiers. There are also differences between indexing systems such as OpenAlex or Crossref, and the national information systems such as the Norwegian CRIS, the bibliographic databases such as the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) or national indexes such as Qualis from Brazil, Publindex in Colombia, or SINTA in Indonesia. Open infrastructures may offer a professional curatorship that allows any indexing system to retrieve the metadata at the document level. On their part, the national curriculum databases such as LATTES, are featured by a different quality in the metadata for scholarly publishing because it is based on the researchers' personal uploading.

Based on its perceived objectivity, Scopus and WoS have been largely considered as the unique citation indexes that can be used as sources of journal authority (Lillis and Curry 2010). For a long time now, they have been contested due to their linguistic, geographical, and disciplinary biases. More recent is the exploration and discussion of their legitimacy as a result of its commercial biases or the finding of questionable journals that were expelled from these collections. In this context, to explore diverse indexation systems and their evaluation criteria is useful to bring back the origins of these collections of quality journals. One of the merits of these lists is their more comprehensive coverage of the scholarly literature of the humanities and social sciences, serving also the aims of documenting and stimulating multilingualism in scholarly publishing (Kulczycki et al., 2020; Sivertsen, 2022).

The national indexes or classification systems managed by the government or funding agencies are relevant sources to inform the quality of a journal, but they all differ in terms of the involvement of the scholarly community, the incidence of the impact indicators in the classifications and the range of journals under assessment (only national or also international journals). A well-established community-based national index is the Norwegian Cristin, an integrated current research information system that includes a qualitative evaluation of all the journals where the Norwegian researchers have published. It is an interesting case because the institutions receive part of their funding through a performance-based redistribution model, so they must report their academic publications every year to the "Norsk vitenskapsindeks" (Norwegian science index). The index classifies them into 2 levels without the use of the Impact Factor. They are awarded Level 1 when they are scholarly quality journals and Level 2 when they

are part of a superior, most prestigious, international journals, which represent the top 20% of all publications in each discipline (Sivertsen, 2018).

The China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) is the largest comprehensive database led by Tsinghua University, containing literature published since 1915. Since 2009, CNKI manages the “International and Domestic Influence of Chinese Academic Journals Statistics and Analysis Database” (CNKI, 2018). This database publishes international and domestic evaluation indicators for nearly 86,000 international academic journals and for more than 6,000 scholarly journals officially published in China. Since 2018, CNKI has also released the “Annual Report for World Academic Journal Impact Index (WAJCI)” which alerts us regarding weather this is a renewed journal ranking. The other list of journals relevant in China is the CAS early-warning list, that became a turning point in 2020, with the first release which included 65 journals as potentially problematic. Chen, Dorsh & Maddi (2025) show a collective and persistent withdrawal from flagged journals, consistent with a reputation trap: once stigmatized, journals experience lasting declines in submissions.

The case of Indonesia is interesting because this country has a significant role in the global diamond scholarly landscape with 1,271 active journals nowadays (according to DOAJ in October 2025). Widiyanto, Hadiyanto, Mantoro y Nugroho (2025) describe the national accreditation system composed of the Science and Technology Index (SINTA) which provides national accreditation although depends heavily in international reputation. The classification system is organized in 6 tiers: SINTA 1: Highest quality journals with scores between 85 and 100. SINTA 2: High-quality journals with scores between 70 and 85. SINTA 3: Good quality journals with scores between 60 and 70. SINTA 4: Moderate quality journals with scores between 50 and 60. SINTA 5: Journals in the development stage with scores between 40 and 50. SINTA 6: Journals with the lowest accreditation scores, ranging from 30 to 40.

The Brazilian *Qualis Periódicos* on its part is a curated and ranked list of all national and international journals in which Brazilian affiliated researchers and postgraduate students have published (Barata, 2016; Brasil, 2023a). It was created by CAPES in 1998 to create a national classification of the journals in order to feed indicators for the accreditation of the postgraduate programs in the country. Throughout its history, Qualis has undergone several changes. The methodology for the current *Qualis Periódicos* (2020) is based on five criteria: 1) a unique classification for each journal; 2) classification established by parent areas; 3) strata obtained from the combination of bibliometric indicators and a mathematical model prepared by CAPES; and 4) bibliometric indicators that consider the number of citations of a journal from Scopus (CiteScore), Web of Science (Impact Factor) and Google Scholar (h-index, both h5 and h10). Based on these five criteria, the classification is divided into eight strata, with each journal falling in a single stratum: A1, the highest, followed by A2, A3, A4, B1, B2, B3, B4, and C, indicating zero weight in the evaluation. Stratum C corresponds to journals that do not have any of the indicators used in the methodology and/or that do not meet the good editorial practices defined

by the *Committee on Publication Ethics* (COPE) and the international databases used in *Qualis Referência* (CAPES, 2020c). Supposedly, Qualis will be extinguished after 2025.

Figure 7

Examples of national indexes/curated journal lists and indexed collections with journal evaluation

The difference between the national indexes and the indexed collections is that the latter provide curated lists of journals after implementing an entrance evaluation with a set of criteria examined to all applicant journals. According with Alonso-Alvarez (2024) AJOL does not define what is a valid peer review nor a minimum set of criteria it has to meet—for instance, whether or not it is anonymous, double- anonymous, or the number of reviewers—but neither does Scopus or WoS (Alonso-Alvarez 2024). WoS and Scopus emphasize editorial quality, technical efficiency and impact, while they are incapable of guaranteeing scholarly mission (or even institutionally based journal) nor academic editorship. Other standards are not clearly met although mentioned in the descriptive documents. Table 1 shows that in contrast, DOAJ, LATINDEX, BIBLAT, REDALYC and SciELO include 8 of the 9 quality standards discussed before. And this takes us to the core of the crisis of the scholarly publishing market, which is not merely the legitimacy of editorial boards. These 5 indexing systems evaluate the academic anchorage of the journal, which frequently defines if the editorial power remains in hands of scholars or may have been transferred to commercial publishers.

Table 1

The diamond quality standards in the evaluation criteria of diverse indexation systems

	1. FUNDING	2. LEGAL OWNERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE	3. OPEN SCIENCE	4. EDITORIAL MANAGEMENT, EDITORIAL QUALITY AND RESEARCH INTEGRITY	5. TECHNICAL SERVICE EFFICIENCY	6. VISIBILITY, COMMUNICATION, MARKETING, AND IMPACT	7. GENDER AND MULTILINGUALISM	8. RESEARCH QUALITY, ACADEMIC EDITORSHIP AND PEER REVIEW	9. ACADEMIC AUTONOMY-SCHOLARLY MISSION, INSTITUTIONAL PUBLISHER
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓	●	●	✓	✗	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓
	●	●	✗	✓	✓	✓	●	●	✗
	●	●	✗	✓	✓	✓	●	●	✗

The four Latin American indexation systems described in Table 1 (Biblat, SciELO, Redalyc, Latindex) share common admission criteria prioritizing that the journals included in their collections are community led journals. All four implement quality evaluations and indexation without citation indicators nor impact factor. The university journal is *par excellence* the journal model fostered by these regional collections. This increases trust although it might not be enough for researchers used to the evaluations by journal rankings. Latindex is a particularly interesting indexation system because it was created as a journal collection and a portal to give them visibility. This means an advantage and a weakness, because the information at the level of journals is well-established, while the metadata at article level is only recently, and partially available². Its governance is based in a regional network with national nodes and decentralized evaluations, expanding to all Ibero-American countries, which gives the system contextualized examinations (Cetto, Alonso Gamboa & Córdoba, 2010). Along its 30 years of existence, Latindex discusses criteria and good practices during its annual meeting which allows us to observe its evolution (Reyna Espinosa & Alonso Gamboa 2025). Latindex not only dedicates efforts to the visibility of the catalogue 2.0 in the portal, and to the admission or retrieval of journals, but also offers free courses and capacity-building for editors and librarians. Noticeably, Latindex created a committee to detect spurious journals, observing suspicious editorial practices and preventing its incidence in the Catalogue 2.0 (Abejón et al., 2024).

² See the new Latindex Article discoverer in: <https://latindex.org/latindex/noticia/344>

Conclusions: creating tools to give value to quality community-led journals

Scholarly publishing emerges in a symbolic field with a legitimation principle that stands in the opposite string of commercial publishing. This is PROBABLY why the commercial publishers have been able to create such high profit marks by recruiting thousands (up to this point maybe millions) of peer-reviewers and editors willing to work *pour l'amour de l'art*. A global tension is nested today between commercial from noncommercial scholarly publishing. And this is at the core of the very definition of diamond journals if we agree on them as community-led journals. However, determining the academic anchorage of a journal is not an easy task because the collaboration between academic organizations and commercial publishers is highly diverse and extended. A severe change underwent behind the expansion of mega-journals and the pledge for fast-track peer review that blurred the original interaction between a given scholarly community and the specific audience of a journal. The homogenization and automatization of editorial management is displacing editors from leading academic decisions. APC prices, payments and waivers, that are hardly transparent, along with the proliferation of predatory journals have affected now directly the collections of Clarivate and Scopus. There is a disturbing undefinition about who are the owners of hundreds of journals, what role the editors play and what is the extent of the intervention of the commercial publishers in the selection of the manuscripts.

Trzesniak (2009) considers editorial boards as pivotal to guaranteeing journal quality standards and safeguarding them from the rising tide of predatory publishing. However, a list of credible scholars in formal academic committees, accompanied by their legitimate contact and affiliation does not ensure credible peer-reviewed scholarly published research. The Latin American experience shows evidence that the difference between community led editorship and commercial publishing (being this predatory or not) resides in the active role of scholars as directors/editors of a journal and the support based in the legitimate anchorage in research or teaching institutions. Academic editorship means alternation among different scholars in these roles and the long-term sustainability of a diamond journal is evidenced in university journals. Rewarding editors and editorial teams at universities while supporting quality journals has become an urgent matter to regain academic control of scholarly publishing. Additionally, the role of the university portals and libraries is critical to provide researchers with informed options of diamond journals.

There is a growing consensus that the Impact Factor must be abolished, and that relevant science cannot be evaluated or measured solely extracting indicators from WoS and Scopus. This is why coverage has become a core issue along with the discussion of the notion of excellence, visibility, and impact. As we have seen, regional indexing services, national information systems and journal indexes are increasingly examined as a path to remedy these biases and as a better means for responsible research assessment (Beigel, 2021; Sivertsen, 2018). To contribute to this research direction and reformist perspective it is critical to have

reliable open infrastructures to shed light on bibliodiversity and multilingual output published in alternative circuits. OpenAlex is a progressive alternative as a collaborative infrastructure that can help to make regional and national data sources visible. But this database is not an indexing system with curated and evaluated collections of quality journals.

In this paper we argued that we need to surpass commercial indexation and seek reliable sources along with rewarding multi-indexed journals. To our understanding, five international indexed collections included in Table 1 (BIBLAT, Redalyc, SciELO, Latindex and DOAJ) comply with editorial and research quality standards and represent consistent lists of quality community-led journals. Moreover, multi-indexed journals, such as is the case of thousands of the diamond journals edited in Latin America that are included in 2 or more of these collections, provide truly reliable reasons to believe that a journal is anchored in the practice of autonomous editorship. To bring back this kind of indexation can be useful to inform researchers and boost diamond scholarly publishing.

Osalzan (2025) proposes an interesting Indexing reform: “Global indexing services must involve editors from non-Western regions in setting selection criteria, ensuring inclusion without compromising rigor”. We would add that a global indexing reform should come as the result of a federated indexing infrastructure formed by noncommercial systems such as DOAJ, Latindex, Redalyc, Scielo, Bblat, along with national indexes and community curated journal lists. We have argued that a potential crisis of legitimacy seems to emerge from the pervasive effects of commercial open access. This places us also in front of an opportunity for radical change.

It doesn't seem advisable to globalize standards of diamond scholarly publishing blurring the diverse starting points of the regions and needs of the different disciplines. One major issue in the debate is the criteria established by DOAS and the DDH related to the persistent identifiers. A relevant part of the diamond journals in Latin American and other Southern regions do not have doi or other identifiers and this is part of the digital world divide. Interoperability, thus, is the goal, but cannot become another barrier. Contextualized solutions and preservation of academic autonomy should prevail, so it becomes more relevant to reach a consensus on diamond principles accepting a diversity: one-size-fits all solution is not advisable.

Our project Diamond Future attempts to focus on the researchers' choices and beliefs, informing about quality diamond journals with proven academic anchorage and editorship. We attempt to provide information about indexation services that evaluate journals by quality in order to foster a change in research assessment and evaluative cultures. But also, we aim to give visibility to the complete landscape of the diamond journals at a global scale, beyond the limits imposed in the traditional databases by the availability of persistent identifiers.

Sustainability is of course a critical issue to assure the continuity of diamond journals and regain control over the journals in hands of the commercial publishers. Several actors are pledging for a new funding system for journals that meet the quality criteria established by the research community (Tautz, Holzer, Schmidt, Buchner, Grötschel & Jurburg 2025). The concept proposed by Leopoldina is interesting because it is meant to complement current funding

models with the aim of replacing them in the long term in the transition to a Diamond Open Access model. But it seems more feasible in the short term to enhance and valorize the existing diamond journals that are already consolidated.

In the context of the increasing marketization of scholarly publishing, the existing diamond journals are at risk and endangered. There is enough evidence of the frequent offers received by academic editors to buy the journals. It is not enough then to foster diamondisation of the journals one-by-one. A more radical change to decommercialize scholarly publishing needs incentives in various directions: a) to diamondize learned society's journals coped by big publishers, b) to sustain technical improvements in quality diamond journals that have no access to permanent identifiers, c) to create federated infrastructures or d) new networked diamond journals.

Inclusive open science deals with two structural obstacles, one dependent on material resources and the other related to the symbolic capital at stake in scientific research. The first obstacle is the global inequalities forged by the digital divide, and the risks of extraction that openness creates for non-hegemonic research communities lacking the indispensable infrastructures for visibility and recognition. The second emerges from the increasing marketization and the domination of the value regimes by infrastructures owned by commercial publishers. These struggles go beyond the tension of the diamond versus the gold routes of open access, and they hit the core of the legitimacy of the scientific field. Therefore, inclusion is ultimately linked to fulfill, eventually, a reform of the pillars of research assessment.

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